

Implementation of Theory of Planned Behavior to Understand Brand love and Its Outcomes

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Abstract

Brand love is considered an influential development for building the customer-brand relationship. The customers are most likely to experience the brand love and this kind of behavior can bring significant advantages for the brands. In this research, 350 respondents participated. This research is carried out with the intention of providing insights about “How the theory planned behavior can be used to understand the brand love, its consequences with their willingness to pay the premium price, level of brand loyalty and enhanced word of mouth?” The predestined objective of this study is to implement the “Theory of Planned Behavior” with respect to brand love. In addition, this study is related to the exploration of the consequences of brand love and moderating role associated with the brand loyalty, willingness to pay the premium price and word of mouth. The exploratory research design is used. In a preliminary study, quantitative methods are specifically used in the study, where statistical data will be used for obtaining results. In this study, data is specifically integrated with the PLS method for analyzing the collected data. Overall results related to planned behavior aspects indicated that there exist statistically significant association between affordability and brand love (P value=0.030), Propensity of anthropomorphize and brand love (P value=0.001) and Subjective Norm and Brand Love (P value=0.006). It is also identified that brand love has statistically significant impact on brand loyalty (P value=0.000) and word of mouth (P value=0.012).

Keywords: brand, attitude, norms, affordability

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the study

The brand love has been receiving greater attention from the last decade as the marketing strategy has shifted from the transactional aspect to the relationship aspect. Previously, the research related to marketing and customer behavior was focused on the interaction of the customers with the brands and the products (Hegner, Fenko, & Teravest, 2017). However, with the advancements of the marketing strategies, the significance of customer involvement has been considered from a relational perspective instead of just focusing on the transactional relationship. In this regard, brand love is considered an influential development for building the customer-brand relationship.

As demonstrated by several researchers, the customers are most likely to experience the brand love and this kind of behavior can bring significant advantages for the brands (Vernuccio, Pagani, Barbarossa, & Pastore, 2015). There are significant outcomes, which are associated with brand love such, willingness to pay the premium price, brand loyalty and word of mouth. The brand loves also ensures brand loyalty in case of any negative information regarding brand equity and reputation. The brand love concept is also considered important by the brand managers as it can drive the customer associated with the brand and thus providing competitive advantages (Bruns, Langner & Fischer, 2017). This is the reason that brand love has become an important emotional advertising strategy by different brands. Yet, despite, the increased recognition of the idea of brand love, several studies are still focused on other strategies and few studies have been conducted on brand love.

These studies considering brand love are usually focused on brand trust and identification and limited research have been carried out on factors facilitating brand love. This is the reason that the focus of this research is to demonstrate the association of planned behavior with brand love and explain the concerns of brand love and its antecedents. By using the planned behavior, the prime focus of this study is on different determinants, which are related to brand love.

1.2. Problem Statement

Hegner, Fenko, and Teravest (2017) revealed that the attitude of customers regarding brand love affect love, which affects the alacrity to pay the premium price, brand loyalty and word of mouth. The subjective norm was considered as an important element for facilitation of brand love and propensity to the anthropomorphise has also had a significant effect on the higher brand love. Vernuccio, Pagani, Barbarossa, and Pastore (2015) mentioned the association between behaviors of the customers and brand love and found that the significant outcomes obtained from brand love include the willingness of consumers to pay a premium price. Langner, Bruns, Fischer, and Rossiter (2016) revealed that formative experiences were associated with the shaping of the trajectories and these included the private, personal and individual experiences of the consumers and in this regard, brand love is considered as a crucial element. Langner, Bruns, Fischer, and Rossiter (2016) demonstrated that there are some similarities and differences associated with the brand love and other types of love and considerable point is that arousing aspects of brand love is less than the interpersonal love.

This is the reason that this research will be carried out with the intention of providing insights into research. The problem statement for this research is, “How the theory planned behavior can be used to understand the brand

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love, its consequences with their level of brand loyalty, willingness to pay the premium price and increased word of mouth?"

1.3. Research Objective

The predestined objective of this study is to implement the "Theory of Planned Behavior" with respect to brand love and its outcome.

1.4. Significance of the Study

Brand love is well-thought-out as a significant element for creating a good brand image as well as preserving forgiveness of the customers in case of failure of the brands. This is therefore significant to evaluate the influence of brand love of consumers to understand the significance of this strategy for retention of loyalty of customers for the brand. This study has its significance as it demonstrates the positive outcomes, which are associated with the brand love of consumers and additionally understand the brand love of consumers to understand the extent of, willingness to pay, brand loyalty and word of mouth. The conceptual model used for this study would provide insights into the processes involved in creating a strong consumer relationship by using different aspects of brand love.

1.5. Outline of the Study

This study is comprised of five chapters, each of which focuses on one of the study's most significant facets. The introduction section makes up the first section of the study. In this part, study aims, objectives, and background are critically evaluated. Information on the value of research, problem identification, and research causes. The "Literature Review" section of the next chapter provides a critical analysis of earlier research findings. The method section is the third component. Research design, sample, sample size, survey structure, and statistical data analysis techniques are the primary topics covered in this chapter. The results section, which appears in the fourth portion of the report, displays the study's findings after data analysis and examines them.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Brand love

As demonstrated by Hegner, Fenko, and Teravest (2017), brand love is considered as the prime element for the purpose of management of brands. They investigated the brand love with respect to the planned behavior theory for the demonstration of the influence of the different elements on brand love such as perceived controlled factors and subjective norms. In addition, the researchers put forward their efforts to evaluate the impact of brand love. 274 individuals who were randomly chosen for this study's survey out of a convenience sample were interviewed. Confirmatory factor analysis, exploratory factor analysis, and modelling methods based on the structural equation were used to test the suggested model for assessing the effect of brand love. The outcomes of this research revealed that the attitude of customers regarding brand love affect love and trust, which affect the involvement of consumers. The subjective norm was considered as an important element for facilitation of brand love and propensity to the anthropomorphise has also had a noteworthy influence on the higher brand love. The planned behavior can be used for evaluation of the brand love and relationship context between brand and customers and this provides a clear understanding about brand love constructs.

2.2. Word of Mouth

There is several research studies focused on the determination of the results of brand love. Most of these studies have demonstrated that the outcomes associated with brand love include the word of mouth, brand loyalty as well as the price premium. The research study carried out by Karjaluoto, Munnukka and Kiuru (2016) carried out a research study to demonstrate the outcomes of brand love and moderating effects of different things on brand love. Based on the consideration of the Carroll and Ahuvia's model, this research was associated with the evaluation of the association between the love for the brand as well as the word of mouth (WOM). The online Facebook survey was carried out for this purpose from 342 participants and the analysis of data obtained by this method was conducted with the use of "partial least squares-structural equation modelling". The outcomes of this research revealed that self-expressiveness for the brand has a significant positive relationship with brand love. Engagement of the customers and this would bring an increase in brand loyalty among customers.

2.3. Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is a prime outcome of the brand love and the level of adherence to any brand has a significant association with brand loyalty and love. In research, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2016) evaluate brand loyalty and its association with the marketing of the brand. The main topic aspects to evaluate the concept of brand loyalty form a broad perspective. This study was based on the multi-method and used the multi-stage approach for the operationalization of the brand. For the research, the qualitative research method has been used along with the administration of a questionnaire from 16 participants. Additionally, the questionnaire was also used for the purpose of collecting the information. Both the qualitative and the quantitative data were analyzed and the outcomes revealed a significant association between the brand loyalty and brand image, love, word of mouth.

2.4. Willingness

Hassey (2016) further put their efforts to demonstrate how the brand characteristics can shape the willingness to pay for the brand. As demonstrated by the research, brand failure is a serious issue, which can result in hefty charges to brand. This research presented that customer expectations and willingness to pay are affected by different brand personalities and violation of these expectations can lead to brand failure and this severity is

controlled by brand love. This research also demonstrated the concept that the competent and warm personalities of the brand are warm personalities and these can elicit the expectation of the customers regarding the performance of the brand; however, the severity of brand failure affects the level of brand loyalty. The experiments were performed to test these concepts and the outcomes demonstrated that consumers can be willing to pay for the brand readily violating their expectations if the brand shows their interest in improving the brand credibility. The brand personality is an imperative to factor in the brand customer willingness to pay and can be used for the effective recovery of the brand.

2.5. Theory of Planned Behavior and its Implementation

As Choo, Ahn, and Petrick (2016) proved, the theory of planned behavior is an extension of the theory of reasoning behavior and one of the most influential theories for interpreting and predicting behavior. The researchers noted that this theory is a comprehensive, but minimalist theory of psychology that defines the causal structure of a wide range of human behavior, including consumer behavior. According to the theory, attitudes, subjective norms and controls affect a person's intention to perform certain behaviors. The intention is reportedly a precursor of behavior. Attitudes toward behavior reflect a favourable or unfavourable assessment of the behavior of a particular behavior. According to the intention of the city council, the intention is a direct influence on behavioral attitudes, subjective norms and control. Subjective norms relate to the perception of general social pressure. If someone else believes that important others support (or disapprove) this behavior, they will have more (or less) an intention to indicate such behavior. Attitudes toward behavior reflect a favourable or unfavourable assessment of the behavior of a particular behavior. In general, the more positive attitude towards behavior, the stronger intention of the person to conduct the act. Giovanis and Athanasopoulou (2018) shown in another study that emotions should inspire behaviour, restrict the amount of information that is processed, and control consumption. The purpose of this study is to investigate how brand love is influenced by subjective standards and controlling variables. The Town Planning Board will completely mediate the attitude, subjective norms, and control elements on the intention, using the will as the direct source of intention. According to the author, wants and emotions serve as incentives for intents and help them direct and drive the outcomes of early occurrences. The greatest predictors of desire, according to the researchers' meta-analysis, are attitudes, subjective standards, and perceptual control. The authors' conclusion is that people take into account social control and coercion when deciding what they want to believe. As a result, the combination of the TPB determinants (love of the brand, regulatory expectations of significant others, and the existence of circumstances that may inhibit or encourage brand love) and the conviction that the brand loves the model is an intriguing study area. The study also shown that companies' self-expression increases brand love since doing so shares personal information with important people.

Shamim, Ghazali, and Albinsson (2016) make the case that attitude is "a generally consistent preference for favourable or unfavourable things, which is the total of predicted results that will be weighted according to the judgement of the attractiveness of results." Consumers are simple to entice because attitude is restricted to the apparent. According to researchers, the fact that ideas are difficult to generate might have an impact on behaviour. The partnership is strong because both parties consistently adore their respective brands. They assume that thinking about and talking about the brand can help you build relationships (Shamim, Ghazali, & Albinsson, 2016). Brand loyalty is influenced favourably by attitude toward brand maintenance. Subjective norms include the idea of a person's importance to others as well as the need to examine your own conduct in light of other people's perceptions that you must act.

2.6. Theoretical Framework

Figure-1

2.7. Hypothesis of the Study

- 2.7.1. H1: Attitude towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on brandlove.
- 2.7.2. H2: Subjective norm towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact onbrand love.
- 2.7.3. H3: Propensity OF Anthropomorphism towards loving a brand has statisticallysignificant impact on brand love.
- 2.7.4. H4: Affordability towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact onbrand love.
- 2.7.5. H5: Brand love has statistically significant impact on brand loyalty.
- 2.7.6. H6: Brand love has statistically significant impact on willingness to pay.
- 2.7.7. H7: Brand love has statistically significant impact on word of mouth.

3. Data Analysis

3.1. Data Analysis

Prime objective associated with the execution of this quantitative research study is to implement the “Theory of Planned Behavior” with respect to brand love. In addition, this study is related to the exploration of the consequences of brand love and moderating role of brand love associated with brand loyalty, willingness to pay premium price and word of mouth. Another objective is to demonstrate the association of brand love and attitude, subjective norm, propensity of anthropomorphize and affordability. The statistical analysis of the data obtained is given in this portion of the research study utilizing tabular and graphical representation. For the purpose of completing this chapter, the following research questions are addressed:

The research questions developed for this research are given below;

- 3.1.1. How does the integration of “theory of planned behavior” can be used to understand consumers’ brand love?
- 3.1.2. What are the consequences of brand love?
- 3.1.3. What is the role of consumers’ brand love in creating the brand loyalty, willingness to pay and word of mouth?

Following research hypothesis are set as according to the set research questions:

- 3.1.4. H1: Attitude towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on outcomes of brand love.
- 3.1.5. H2: Subjective norm towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on outcomes of brand love.
- 3.1.6. H3: Propensity OF Anthropomorphism towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on outcomes of brand love.
- 3.1.7. H4: Affordability towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on outcomes of brand love.
- 3.1.8. H5: Brand love has statistically significant impact on brand loyalty.
- 3.1.9. H6: Brand love has statistically significant impact on willingness to pay.
- 3.1.10. H7: Brand love has statistically significant impact on word of mouth.

3.2. Demographic Analysis

350 people took part in the survey and data gathering procedure. A total of 350 respondents participated, as shown by the answers to the questions on demographics and sample characteristics.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

		What is your gender?	What is age?	What is your education?
N	Valid	350	350	350
	Missing	0	0	0

159 male respondents and 191 female respondents out of 350 total respondents took part in the data gathering procedure. According to the survey's findings, the majority of the respondents were women. The differences between the sexes, however, are marginally different.

It is clear from the data that the respondents who took part in the survey procedure belonged to various age groups. 130 of the respondents were under the age of 20, 68 were between the ages of 20 and 30, and 87 said they were between the ages of 31 and 40. 65 responders were above the age of 40, making up the largest demographic. The findings showed that respondents from a variety of backgrounds were chosen at random from the pool of respondents.

Respondents were asked to identify their education level. According to the results, it is identified that 95 respondents were under graduate, 88 were graduate, 88 were post graduate and 79 of the respondents indicated that they possess other qualification degrees.

Table 2: Demographic Summary of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
<i>Gender</i>	Male	159	45.2	45.2	45.2
	Female	191	54.8	54.8	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	
<i>Age</i>	Below 20	130	37.1	37.1	37.1
	20 -29	68	19.4	19.4	55.2
	30 – 39	87	24.8	24.8	82.0
	40 and Above	65	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	
<i>Education</i>	Undergraduate	95	28.0	28.0	28.0
	Graduate	88	25.2	25.2	53.2
	Post Graduate	88	25.2	25.2	78.4
	Others	79	21.6	21.6	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

3.3. Model Measurement

When evaluating reliability while utilising a reflective structure, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and mean variance extraction (AVE) were used. For consistency dependability to be considered adequate, Cronbach's alpha must be at least 0.7. Cronbach's alpha does have limitations, though, since it typically overestimates the dependability of internal consistency. Internal consistency reliability may also be measured using composite dependability. Acceptable range for the composite dependability rating is 0.7–0.9. The focus of convergent validity, on the other hand, is on incorporating outside loadings and assessing if there is a positive connection between one indicator and others of the same structure. The effectiveness of convergence to a particular level is evaluated using AVE. According to the indicator's variance, the composition is deemed to be at least 50% when AVE is greater than 0. (Hair et al., 2014). If removal has no effect on composite dependability, the indicator should be kept and taken into consideration to be between 0.4 and 0.7. Indicators and outer loadings must be bigger than 0.708. To define unique and divergent occurrences and assess how different a structure is from other structures, discriminant validity is utilized (Hair et al., 2014). There are two ways to assess how successful discriminating is. The first is that, according to the indication, the load on all other structures must be larger than the external load.

3.4. Convergent Validity

It is determined that the values for outer loadings exceed 0.5 based on the convergent validity results of the research's included variable. Additionally, it can be seen that the variables' composite reliability surpasses 0.7, meeting the criteria of the rule of thumb. The next table also shows that Cronbach alpha values and AVE values both surpass 0.7. These overall results show that the research model's constructs are compatible with the statistical tests' requirements for reliability and validity.

Table 3: Convergent validity

Cronbach'sAlpha		rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Affordability	0.938	0.960	0.956	0.844
Attitude	0.932	0.949	0.951	0.830
Brand love_	0.929	0.938	0.955	0.875
Brand loyalty	0.939	0.940	0.961	0.892
Propensity of anthropomorphize	0.937	0.943	0.955	0.842
Subjective norm	0.927	0.939	0.953	0.872
Willingness	0.896	1.225	0.916	0.786
Wom	0.701	0.726	0.869	0.768

3.5. Discriminant Validity

Cross loading of indicators, heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlation, Fornell & Larcker criteria, and cross loading of indicators are the two different tests that may be used to assess the validity of a discriminant. The Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio utilised in this study measures discriminant validity in addition to these two specific tests. The tables below list the results of the data collection in terms of discriminant validity.

According to Haenlein and Kaplan (2004), discriminant validity requires a precise Average Variance Extracted analysis. The purpose of this test is to determine whether any latent constructions have any connections that are stronger than the square root of each AVE for each individual construct. According to the general rule of thumb, the square root of each construct included in the model should be higher than the value discovered while correlating that construct with another construct. Furthermore, the construct must have a value of at least 0.50. As all values are larger than 0.5, the findings also address the general condition for discriminant validity.

Table 4:Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Affordability	Attitude	Brand Love_	Brand Loyalty	Propensity of Anthropomorphize	Subjective Norm	Willingness	WOM
Affordability	0.918							
Attitude	0.323	0.911						
Brand Love_	0.246	0.285	0.936					
Brand Loyalty	0.296	0.361	0.279	0.944				
Propensity Of Anthropomorphize	0.254	0.404	0.339	0.327	0.918			
Subjective Norm	0.361	0.446	0.292	0.465	0.318	0.934		
Willingness	0.067	0.711	0.033	0.088	0.120	0.193	0.887	
WOM	0.006	0.289	-0.12	0.055	0.003	-0.040	0.498	0.876

The cross loading technique is also used to assess the discriminant validity of the model's integrated concept. The cross loading value for each build should, in general, be more than 0.70. The findings showed that, with a few exceptions, every other components in the model had values greater than 0.70. Additionally, this test confirms that cross loading is required for each construct in the model.

Table 5: Cross Loadings

	Affordability	Attitude	Brand Love_	Brand Loyalty	Propensity Of Anthropomorphize	Subjective Norm	Willingness	WOM
A1	0.286							
A2	0.285							
A3	0.349							
A4	0.257							
AFF1		0.297						
AFF2		0.294						
AFF3		0.278						
AFF4		0.315						
AN1			0.309					
AN2			0.311					
AN3			0.343					
AN4			0.277					
BL1				0.254				
BL2				0.292				
BL3				0.232				
BRL1					0.301			
BRL2					0.315			
BRL3					0.309			
SN1						0.924		
SN2						0.937		
SN3						0.940		
WL1							0.882	
WL2							0.796	
WL3							0.973	
WOM1								0.905
WOM2								0.846

The HTMT correlation ratio is another tool for evaluating discriminant validity. According to the general recommendation for this particular test, HTMT levels shouldn't be higher than 0.90.

Table 6: HeterotraitMonotrait Ratio

	Affordability	Attitude	Brand Love_	Brand Loyalty	Propensity of Anthropomorphize	Subjective Norm	Willingness	Wom
Affordability								
Attitude	0.345							
Brand Love_	0.257	0.300						
Brand Loyalty	0.309	0.378	0.296					
Propensity of Anthropomorphize	0.270	0.432	0.359	0.349				
Subjective Norm	0.380	0.475	0.308	0.499	0.343			
Willingness	0.059	0.794	0.029	0.075	0.148	0.181		
WOM	0.028	0.361	0.148	0.070	0.027	0.050	0.662	

3.6. Coefficient of Determination

The evaluation of the Pearson coefficient or the value of R² serves as the initial coefficient of determination analysis. The ratio of variance of the dependent variable contained in the structural model was evaluated by the R square value. The value of R square, according to Götz, Liehr-Gobbers, and M. Krafft (2010), indicates the calibre of the modified model. The Q² indicator evaluates the model's precision and the calibre of predictions. As a general rule, it is said that the value for Q² should be greater than 0. According to the table, it is identified that R square value for Service Quality is 0.609 indicating moderate predictive accuracy of the model. Moreover, Q square value exceeds zero indicating higher prediction of quality of the model.

Table 7: Blindfolding and Coefficient of Determination

	R Square	Q
Brand Love_	0.172	0.162
Brand Loyalty	0.078	0.075
Willingness	0.001	-0.002
Wom	0.014	0.012

3.7. Structural Model

Results for the path coefficient are obtained using PLS in order to test the study's predetermined hypothesis. Researchers can determine how an independent variable affects a dependent variable using the path coefficient. The effects of attitude, subjective norm, anthropomorphize, and affordability on brand love are shown in the following table. The findings show that customer attitude has a negligible effect on brand love, with a p value greater than 0.05. This conclusion showed that the alternative hypothesis is not supported by the data sufficiently to adopt it. Therefore, based on the findings, it is established that brand love results are not statistically significantly impacted by brand attitude. The findings also show that brand love is statistically significantly impacted by subjective norm. The findings show that, with a p value less than 0.005, the subjective norm of liking a brand has no statistically significant effect on the consequences of brand love.

Table 8: Path Coefficients

	Original ample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Decision
Affordability > Brand Love_	0.106	0.103	0.049	2.180	0.030	Accepted
Attitude > Brand Love_	0.097	0.103	0.061	1.598	0.111	Rejected
Brand Love > Brand Loyalty	0.279	0.285	0.067	4.166	0.000	Accepted
Brand Love > Willingness	0.033	0.029	0.077	0.421	0.674	Rejected
Brand Love > WOM	-0.120	-0.127	0.047	2.533	0.012	Accepted
Propensity of Anthropomorphize -> Brand Love_	0.229	0.237	0.066	3.459	0.001	Accepted
Subjective Norm -> Brand Love_	0.138	0.136	0.050	2.756	0.006	Accepted

The influence of anthropomorphizing and its statistical testing on brand love were also found in the results. As the p-value is less than 0.05, the results show that the tendency to anthropomorphize has a substantial influence on

brand love. Results support the idea that brand love outcomes are not statistically significantly impacted by a person's propensity to anthropomorphize brands. The results of the data collection show that brand love outcomes are statistically significantly impacted by affordability toward liking a brand.

In order to test the hypothesis regarding the impact of brand love on brand loyalty, willingness and word of mouth path coefficient results are attained through using PLS. According to the results it identified that brand love possess statistically significant association with brand loyalty. , as significant value is less than 0.05. Hence hypothesis claiming that brand love has statistically significant associated with brand loyalty is accepted. According to the results it identified that brand love possess statistically not significant association with word of mouth. , as significant value is higher than 0.05. Hence hypothesis claiming that brand love has statistically significant associated with word of mouth is failed to accepted. However, results indicated that brand love has not statistically significant association with willingness of the consumers to pay more. Overall, the results attained through data collected and executing statistical testing identified following outcomes for hypothesis set for this research:

Table 9: Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Decision
H1: Attitude towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on brand love.	Rejected
H2: Subjective norm towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on brand love.	Accepted
H3: Propensity OF Anthropomorphism towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on brand love.	Accepted
H4: Affordability towards loving a brand has statistically significant impact on brand love.	Accepted
H5: Brand love has statistically significant impact on brand loyalty.	Accepted
H6: Brand love has statistically significant impact on willingness to pay.	Accepted
H7: Brand love has statistically significant impact on word of mouth.	Rejected

4. Discussion

The data gathered throughout the data gathering procedure is thoroughly examined in this phase of the study. Several statistical tests were run using PLS to extract useful information from the data collected from the respondents. Different findings that test the predetermined research hypothesis are identified based on the examination of the outcomes. The results show a substantial correlation between brand love and brand loyalty as well as readiness to spend. The theory of planned behaviour is one of the most prominent theories for understanding and predicting behaviour, as demonstrated by Choo, Ahn, and Petrick (2016). It is an extension of the idea of rational behaviour. According to the notion, a person's desire to do certain activities to engage in brand love can be influenced by attitudes, subjective standards, and controls.

The study's first premise contends that brand love is statistically significantly influenced by one's attitude about a product or service. The study's findings indicate that customer attitude has no discernible influence on brand love with a p value greater than 0.05. The study's findings go counter to those of Hegner, Fenko, and Teravest's (2017) investigation, which found that consumer engagement is influenced by the way in which people feel about their favourite brands.

The study's second hypothesis contends that brand love is statistically influenced by one's subjective standard for appreciating a particular product or service. The data show that brand love is statistically significantly impacted by subjective norm. This study's findings are consistent with the argument made by Vernuccio, Pagani, Barbarossa, and Pastore (2015), who identified subjective norm as a crucial factor in the promotion of brand love. According to the study's findings, companies need to address subjective norms of customers as one of the crucial aspects of addressing the elements that affect consumers' attitudes and general behaviour in order to develop brand loyalty.

According to the third premise of the study, brand loyalty is statistically influenced by one's predisposition for anthropomorphizing brands. The study's findings show that the predisposition to anthropomorphize one's love of a brand has a statistically significant effect on the consequences of brand love. The study's conclusions corroborate those of the research of Hegner, Fenko, and Teravest (2017). Hegner, Fenko, and Teravest's (2017) research indicates that predisposition to anthropomorphize has also had a substantial impact on increased brand love.

The study's fourth hypothesis said that brand love is statistically significantly impacted by affordability toward loving a brand. The results of the data collection show that brand love outcomes are statistically significantly impacted by affordability toward liking a brand. Overall, it was shown that all variables, with the exception of attitude, had statistically significant effects on the outcomes of brand love.

The fifth hypothesis of the study holds that brand love affects consumer brand loyalty in a statistically meaningful way. The results of the study show that brand love affects brand loyalty in a statistically meaningful way. Brand

loyalty was statistically verified based on findings with a p-value of less than 0.05, which demonstrated that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The study's findings supported those of a study by Siamagka and Christodoulides (2016) that found a substantial association between brand love and brand loyalty. Customers who are loyal to a brand are more ready to overlook its mistakes. By defining brand love in the context of customer brand loyalty, the findings of the current study have improved the field.

According to the sixth premise of the study, brand loyalty influences customers' desire to spend money in a statistically significant way. The results of the study demonstrate that brand loyalty has a statistically significant impact on willingness to pay. Brand loyalty was statistically verified based on findings with a p-value of less than 0.05, which demonstrated that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The study's findings supported those of a study by Siamagka and Christodoulides (2016) that found a substantial association between brand love and brand loyalty. Customers who are loyal to a brand are more ready to overlook its mistakes. By defining brand love in the context of customer brand loyalty, the findings of the current study have improved the field. The study's final hypothesis claimed that word-of-mouth was statistically significantly influenced by brand loyalty. The results of the study show that brand love has a statistically significant impact on word-of-mouth.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This section of the research provides comprehensive insights with the answers of the research questions set for executing this research study. These section summaries the findings of the study and also cover the managerial implications and suggestions for future research with aspect to Implementation of Theory of Planned Behavior.

5.1. Conclusion

This study has its significance as it demonstrates the positive outcomes, which are associated with the brand love of consumers and additionally understand the behavior of involved consumers to understand the extent of brand loyalties. The conceptual model used for this study would provide insights into the processes involved in creating a strong consumer relationship by using different aspects of brand love.

5.2. Managerial implications

This research study and the results attained through this research has been successful in evaluating and identifying the association of each dependent and independent variable that are included in the theory of planned behavior model. The results of this research study possess meaningful implications for retail industry, managers as well as for the academia. The information and meaningful knowledge attained through this research study will enable scholar to analyze and understand the variable with respect to understanding consumer behavior theory. In addition to this, the outcomes of this research study will enable retailers to understand the significance of different actions that will result in desired consumer behavior. It is crucial for managers and retailers to understand the knowledge related to managing different channels and implementing different marketing approaches for influencing the preferences of consumers.

5.3. Future Recommendations

For future research study, it is recommended to expand through integrating diverse ethnic groups of Pakistan and also focus on specific age group of sample population. In addition to this, it is recommended for future research study to analyze different sample cohorts. Likewise different statistical analysis could be used for executing more comprehensive analysis of variable including Structural Equation Modeling and Hierarchical Linear Modeling (HLM). Moreover, it is also recommended for future research studies to focus on different industry and consumer segments including clothing and online retail industry.

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